

Conceptual Study of Role of Gandhakadi Malahara In Dadru

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 24 April 2021	<i>Dadru</i> is one of the common skin diseases mentioned in <i>Ayurveda</i> . In <i>Ayurveda Twak Sharir</i> holds important place. <i>Ayurvedic</i> literatures have described <i>Twak Sharir</i> with various types of <i>Kushtha</i> according to layers of skin. <i>Dadru</i> is a type of <i>Kushtha</i> which mainly affects the 4th layer among the six layers of the skin. In modern science the clinical manifestation of <i>Dadru</i> is closely related to local fungal/tinea infection which is affecting upto 15% of population. Excessive severe itching and ring shaped red patches are the common manifestation which can be diagnosed by <i>Darshana</i> and <i>Prashana</i>
Corresponding Author: Dr. Akanksha Tripathi	<i>Pariksha</i> . Management includes <i>Shodhan</i> , <i>Shaman</i> and <i>Bahirparimarjan Chikitsa</i> . Among them <i>Shaman</i> measures in the form of <i>Lepa</i> (topical applications) are widely prescribed. In present study <i>Gandhakadi Malhar</i> is selected as Topical application.
KEYWORDS: Dadru, Twaka, Kushtha, Tinea	

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda is most ancient system of medicine in the world. *Ayurveda* advocates a complete promotive, preventive and curative system of medicine. In *Ayurveda Twak Sharir* holds important place. *Ayurvedic* literatures have described *Twak Sharira* with various types of

Kushtha according to layers of skin.

Skin diseases are common manifestation in present era. Patient of skin disease are additionally prone to experience physical, emotional and socioeconomic embarrassment in society due to disfigured appearance. Normally 10-15% of general practitioner encounter with skin disorder in day to day practice most common among them is fungal infection. In *Ayurveda* skin fungal infection (*Tinea/Ringworm*) is termed as *Dadru*.

Dadru is a skin disease which harms and deforms the skin. *Dadru* is one of the sub-type among

the eighteen types of *Kushtha Roga* described in *Ayurveda* classics.

According to all *Ayurvedacharya's Kushtha* is described as a synonym for all skin diseases as:-

Disease which causes discoloration and degeneration of the skin. *Dadru* is a type of *Kushtha* which mainly affects the 4th layer among the six layers of the skin according to *Acharya Charaka*. *Dadru* has been considered as *Mahakushtha* according to *Acharya Sushruta* and *Vagbhat* and *Ksudra Kushtha* according to *Acharya Charaka*. Clinical features of

Dadru involve *Kandu*, *Raag*, *Utsann Mandal Deerghapataan*, *Pidika*. The main *Doshas* in *Dadru* is *Pitta-Kapha* according to *Acharya Charaka* and *Kapha* by *Acharya Sushrut* and *Vagbhatt*. *Acharya Vagbhatt* especially mentioned *Dadru* as *Anushangika*.

According to pilot study of various *Samhitas* and modern literatures it is seen that symptoms of *Dadru* and *tinea/Ringworm* shows tremendous similarity with each other. The correlation of *Dadru* and *tinea* is done on the basis of similarity of symptoms and histopathological investigations. The result found are *Dadru* and *tinea* have almost all the sign and symptoms which are correlated on the basis of literary and clinical study of both *Ayurveda* and modern science.

In *Ayurvedic* texts management of *Dadru* includes *Shodhan*, *Shaman* and *Bahirparimarjan Chikitsa*. Among them *Shaman* measures in *Lepa* (topical applications) are widely prescribed. Topical applications are more useful in *Twak Vikaras* as they directly act on the affected parts or lesion and due to its physiological affect of heat on skin. Internal medicine is also necessary to bring homeostasis in vitiated *Dosha* and *Dushyas*.

The article explains the role of *Gandhakadi Malhara* is selected as Topical application. This *Malhara* is described as *Dadruhar* as per *Rastarangini*.

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MATERIAL AND METHOD

Various *Ayurvedic* texts reviewed for this study are *Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita, Ashtanga Hridaya, Rastarangini, Chakradatta, Bhela Samhitamhita, Madhav Nidana, Harita Samhita.*

Apart from this relevant modern medical science book and websites have also been used for it.

NIDANA OF DADRU:

1. Primary causes of Dadru:

As per *Ayurveda Acharyas* not explained separate *Nidana* for *Dadru Kushtha*, but *Dadru*

2. Secondary causes of Dadru: As per Ayurveda Acharyas

<i>Mithya Ahara</i>	Ch.S	Su.S	B.S	H.S	M.N
Adhyashana	+	+	-	+	+
Vishamasana	+	+	-	-	-
Atyashana	+	+	-	-	-
<i>Ajeernashana</i>	+	+	-	-	+
Continous ans excessive use of Madhu, Fanita, Matsya, Lakucha, Mulaka, Kakmachi	+	-	-	-	-
Excessive Snehana	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Vidahi Ahara without emesis of undigested food</i>	+	-	+	+	-
<i>Rasataha</i>					
Excessive intake of <i>Amla</i> and <i>Lavana Rasa</i>	+	-	-	-	+
<i>Dravyataha</i>					
<i>Excessive intake of Gramya, Anoop, Audaka, Mamsa</i>	-	-	+	-	-
<i>Navanna, Dadhi, Guda, Tila, Mulak, Matsya</i>	+	-	-	-	+
<i>Dushivisha</i>	-	+	-	-	-
<i>Dushita Jala</i>	-	-	-	+	-
<i>Gunataha</i>					
<i>Excessive Drava, Snigdha, Ahara</i>	+	-	-	+	+
<i>Guru Ahara</i>	+	+	-	-	+

As per Modern Science *tinea corporis*, weak immune system, poor nutrition, stress, obesity, contact with contagious are some secondary causes of *tinea* infection.

RUPA

Itchy, red, eruptive lesions and patches are *Dadru Kushtha*. Elevataed patches with pruritus which resemble like root of *Durva* grasses and *Atasi* (flax) flower is *Dadru Kushtha*.

Samprapti of Dadru

Kushtha spread person to person by *Malaja Krimi* through *sweda*(contact with infected person).

As per modern Ringworm is a contagious fungal infection caused by mold like parasites that live on the cell in outer layer of skin. And it can be spread by human to human , animal to human , by touching the infected objects, due to sharing towel,bedsheets,soap etc of infected person causes spreading of microorganism from one person to another or from soil infected with fungus.

Acharya Sushruta mentioned *Dadru Vyadhi* under *Mahakushtha* which is characterised by more itching sensation as like pain. In *Dadru* colour of skin look like as *Atasi* flower or as *Tamra* which are spreading in nature and are associated with *Pidik*.

GANDHAKADI MALAHARA

Drug	Rasa	Guna	Virya	Vipaka	Dosha Karma	Pharmacological action	Therapeutic use
Shuddha Gandhaka	Katu, Tikta Kashaya	Sara	Ushna	Madhura	PittaVardhaka Kapha-vatahara	Antifungal Antimicrobial	Dadru, Kandu Kushtha, Pama, Krimi Aamdosha
Sphatika	Katu, Amla Kashaya, Madhura	Guru Snigdha	Ushna	Madhura	Tridosahara	Styptic Astringent Antiseptic	Twakroga, Shwitra Keshya
Tankana	Kshariya	Ruksha Tikshna Guru	Ushna	Katu	Pittakara Vatahara Kaphanissaraka	Expectorant Antidote	Twakroga
Saal ki Raal	Kashaya Madhura	Ruksha	Sheeta	Katu	PittaKaphahara	bactericidal	Kushtha, Atisweda
Nimbu	Amla	Tikshna	Ushna	Amla	Kaphavatahara	Antifungal Antioxidant	Twakroga Aruchi

DISCUSSION

In this article we can study the concept that by application of Gandhakadi Malahara pacifies the Doshas and leads to the breaking of Samprapti, which helps in reducing the symptoms like Kandu, Pidika. Rasa and Raktashodhak, Varnya, Lekhan, Shothahara properties of Malahara pacifies Dushyas and which help in reducing the symptoms like Raga and Mandala.

The content of Malahara possess Snigdha, Tikshna, Ruksha, Sara, Ushna, Tridosahar properties. All the ingredients of Malahara have pharmacologically an antifungal, antimicrobial, antipruritic, antiodot, antioxidant action hence can effectively reduce the infection and prevent its recurrence by improving the immunity of skin by its antioxidant property.

Shudha Gandhak is Antifungal, Antimicrobial. Vital role in immune system, helps in detoxification. It helps in tissue repair and referred to as ‘Nature’s beauty mineral’. **Sphatika Bhasma** is Antiseptic, Antipruritic, Anti-inflammatory, regulates excessive sweating, Antimicrobial **Shudha Tankana** is Antifungal, antibacterial. **Saal Nirayasa** Used in Atisweda. The bark extract of *Shorea robusta* is widely used in preparation of antifungal drug. **Nimbu Swarasa** is It has an antiseptic, antioxidant and antifungal abilities.

Upon topical application, active principle of Malahara release deeper tissue through siramukh and swedavahi shrotas with its Sara and Tikshna property. Due to Ushna, Tikshna, Sara property it remove the obstruction in Swedawahi Shrotas and allow local toxin to flow through sweda thus clearing out the microchannels .

Ushna Virya of Malahara and of vehicle of lemon causes pacification of Kapha which forms Samprapti Vighatan thus alleviating the symptoms. Topical preparation applied might have acted by Ruksh, Tikshna property for pacifying Kapha Dosha locally and maintain equilibrium of other Dosha.

After local action, the impaired Dhatwagni of Rasa, Rakta might be corrected to some extent by Agnideepana property

of Gandhaka and vehicle Nimbu. By this Dhatu Shaithilya might have reduced and provide nourishment to Twacha.

KANDU-caused by vitiated Kapha and Katu, Tikta, Kashaya, Kandughna and Kushthaghna, Kaphashamak, Ushna Virya help to reduce symptoms.

RAGA- it is due to Pitta Prakopa and Sheet, Madhur, Tikta, Rasa, Rakta Shodhaka and Raktaprasadak, Deepan, Pachan property of Malahara help to reduce Raga.

PIDIKA-it is due to Pitta-Kapha Pradhan Tridosha vitiation and Ushna, Ruksha, Sheet, Tikshana Guna of Malahara reduce the symptoms.

MANDAL-due to vitiated Tridosha and Kushthaghn, Twakdosahara, Raktadosahar pacify the symptoms

CONCLUSION

Dadru is most common skin disease for which complete cure till date is not available due to its high recurrence rate and due to development of resistance among the patients for the antibiotics that are being used after sometime. Almost all the Acharyas has mentioned Dadru along with its management So it is a need of hour to find effective, permanent and promisable Ayurvedic treatment for Dadru or tinea infection that can prevent their recurrence also.

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